

AI for Global Health: Leveraging Large Language Models for Tuberculosis Treatment Adherence

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ABSTRACT

Tuberculosis (TB) is the leading cause of death from an infectious disease globally, with the highest burden in low- and middle-income countries. In these regions, limited healthcare access and high patient-to-treatment supporter ratios impede effective patient support, communication, and treatment completion. To bridge this gap, we propose integrating a specialized Large Language Model into an efficacious digital adherence technology to augment interactive communication with treatment supporters. This AI-powered approach, operating within a human-in-the-loop framework, aims to enhance patient engagement and improve TB treatment outcomes. Here, we present our development, evaluation considerations, and preliminary analysis of the LLM-powered conversational TB agent, developed specifically for Argentinian linguistic and cultural settings.

KEYWORDS

Large Language Models; Tuberculosis; Digital Adherence Technologies; Health Applications of AI

INTRODUCTION

Tuberculosis (TB) remains the world's deadliest infectious disease, despite being preventable and curable (World Health Organization (WHO), 2023). Efforts to meet the WHO's 2030 targets for TB diagnosis and treatment have fallen short (Fukunaga et al., 2021), resulting in continued transmission and loss of life. The burden is disproportionately high in low- and middle-income countries, where healthcare systems face significant challenges.

Digital Adherence Tools (DATs) - including feature phone-based and smartphone-based chat applications - have emerged as a promising solution to maintain effective patient-provider communication and support the patients during the demanding 6- to 9-month treatment. These tools put additional strain on the medical professionals, necessitating manual supervision and responses to the patients' on-demand questions. Large Language Models (LLMs) offer promising potential to augment existing chatbot-based DATs, generating real-time, human-like response suggestions for the overburdened healthcare workers, making communication easier (Figure 1). However, the effectiveness of LLMs as comprehensive digital adherence tool remains underexplored, particularly in non-English healthcare settings. This gap is especially relevant for TB treatment, as many countries with the highest TB burden do not use English as their primary language (Huddart, MacLean & Pai, 2016).

Our study has two primary objectives:

1. Develop an LLM-powered TB treatment support tool for Argentinian settings based on real-world data and patient needs, using multiple in-context learning techniques.
2. Comprehensively evaluate the resulting model.

Figure 1. Project Setup

METHODS

This mixed-methods study details the iterative design and preliminary evaluation of models for our AI-assisted TB-DAT. Table 1 describes resulting models.

Model	Prompt Structure
0	Zero-Shot (English)
1	Zero-Shot
2	Few-Shot
3	RAG
4	RAG + Few-Shot
5	RAG + Few-Shot + Two-Step Classification

Table 1. Description of each model tested

In-Context Learning

Due to space constraints, we cannot provide prompts here, however we followed previous work by Nori et al. (2023). We employed zero-shot, few-shot, and RAG techniques to adapt a generalist GPT-based LLM to a medical task. Zero-shot prompts provided an instruction-based baseline, while few-shot (FS) (Brown et al., 2020) incorporated patient dialogues for greater personalization. RAG enhanced knowledge-intensive responses by integrating external TB resources. A combined agentic approach shown in Figure 2 was made to simultaneously improve medical accuracy and empathy of the responses by redirecting the user's input to specialized AI agents. However, it does introduce additional considerations, since questions that heavily contain both informational and emotional elements may be classified as only one of these types, leading to either too formal or less information-heavy response than necessary.

Figure 2. Multi-Agent system

EVALUATION

Due to the scope of this workshop, we focus our discussion on linguistic accuracy evaluation and omit other categories. We adapt the QUEST evaluation framework developed by Tam et al. (2024) based on their LLM literature review of research work spanning the last 6 years to evaluate our models.

Evaluation	Category	Definition	Scoring
Internal Evaluation	Linguistic Accuracy	The conversation agent's responses were idiomatically correct, incorporating details of Argentinian dialect.	<p>Low: Apparent lack of understanding of Spanish language</p> <p>Moderate: Uses neutral Spanish, lacks Argentinian variety features</p> <p>High: Model incorporates Argentinian Spanish features</p>
External Evaluation	Understanding	The conversation agent correctly interpreted my questions and provided appropriate responses.	<p>Likert Scale</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Strongly Disagree 2. Disagree 3. Neutral 4. Agree 5. Strongly Agree
	Clarity	The conversation agent's responses were clear and understandable for patients with varying levels of medical literacy.	
	Language	The conversation agent's responses were idiomatically correct and sounded natural in Spanish.	

Table 2. Linguistic Accuracy Evaluation Framework

The models were assessed in two stages. The six initial models shown in Table 1 were deployed and evaluated according to the Linguistic Accuracy category shown in Table 2 during a period of two weeks. The clinical evaluation team consisted of a licensed physician, a nurse trained in empathy, and an Argentinian resident, all with Spanish as a primary language. The evaluators asked the models questions that were representative of Argentinian TB patient-to-doctor conversations collected in a previous trial (Iribarren et al. 2022). After this internal evaluation, we chose the 3 most promising models (Models 2, 4, and 5) to undergo external evaluation. Five external evaluators, also with background in medicine and with Spanish as a primary language, were asked to interact with the model using different TB patient personas, three personas per model.

RESULTS

Quantitative Evaluation

Table 3 and Table 4 present the models' evaluation results using the categories outlined in Table 2 during two stages of evaluations: internal evaluation (3 internal clinical team members) performed based on GPT-3.5 models and external evaluation (5 external clinical professionals) performed based on GPT-4 models as they became available.

Model	Prompt Structure	Linguistic Accuracy	Pronouns
0	Zero-Shot (English)	High	voseo
1	Zero-Shot	Moderate	usted
2	Few-Shot	Moderate	usted
3	RAG	Very Low	tú
4	RAG + Few-Shot	Moderate	usted
5	RAG + Few-Shot + Classification	Moderate	usted

Table 3. Internal Evaluation Results

Dimension	Model 2 (Std Dev)	Model 4 Avg (Std Dev)	Model 5 Avg (Std Dev)
Understanding	4.93 (0.26)	4.60 (0.74)	4.67 (0.82)
Clarity	4.87 (0.35)	4.27 (1.22)	4.87 (0.35)
Language	4.87 (0.35)	5.00 (0.00)	4.93 (0.26)

Table 4. External Evaluation Results

Qualitative Evaluation

Internal Evaluation

The models generally demonstrated correct grammar and contextually relevant vocabulary in their responses, effectively aligning with the Spanish dialect spoken in Argentina. This was evident in the terminology used to refer to the health system, healthcare facilities, medical professionals, symptoms, and treatment side effects. Responses felt natural and relatable to users.

Pronoun usage: A notable limitation persisted in the use of the formal pronoun *tú* (you) and its associated verb conjugations, instead of adapting to the informal *vos* (you) or the formal *usted* and maintaining consistent pronoun and verb conjugation coherence. Specifically, when attempting to use the Argentine *vos* form, the models sometimes reverted to *tú* or *usted* within the same interaction. The complexity of the *voseo* paradigm lies in its variable impact across verb tenses and its dependence on geographical and social factors. The singular *usted* is the standard form in formal contexts in both Latin America and Spain. A model’s inability to adapt to either informal *vos* or general *usted* limits its ability to align with the linguistic norms expected by users in Argentina. Model 0 explicitly uses *voseo* (e.g., “tenés”) as used in Argentina, making its responses feel more approachable and natural.

Stereotyping. The AI model displayed inconsistency in gender-inclusive forms such as *médico/a* (physician) or *enfermero/a* (nurse) when referring to healthcare professions. In Spanish, nouns ending in *-o* in the masculine form typically change to *-a* in the feminine. This convention applies to professions and roles to ensure grammatical agreement between the noun’s gender and its referent. By defaulting to the masculine form (*médico*), the model exhibited a gender bias toward masculine defaults.

External Evaluation

In analyzing the free-text responses from the participants, the most common finding was the use of overly scientific language and/or language that is inappropriate for low medical literacy. Table 5 lists the most encountered codes and exemplary quotes. The use of inappropriate medical language was noted two times in model 2 and eight times in model 4. Additionally, researchers noted the language was sometimes in an Argentinian dialect in model 2, but not always. Researchers described all models as having long answers. At the same time, the answers could be vague, especially regarding how to prevent the spread of TB. Models 2 and 4 both made the mistake of providing answers for latent TB when the participant was asking about active TB treatment. Model 5 made this mistake despite being corrected by the participant. Participants described the responses from models 2 and 4 as potentially dangerous. Specifically, they highlighted how the models made recommendations to take medications without obtaining further clarification from patients on important matters, such as allergies.

Table 5. Codes Derived from Qualitative Evaluation

Codes	Number of times code mentioned	Example Quotes (Translated)
Use of technical/scientific language	10	“Answer to detailed for patient with low literacy.” “Presence of some technical terms that could be confusing for patients with low literacy” “Answers not always comprehensible to non-medical populations, too scientific”
Confused latent/active TB	4	“The model assumed I had latent TB when I told it I had been diagnosed with TB” “The diagnostic tests recommended were PPD, IGRA, it did not recommend a sputum sample”
Vague answer	3	“In some instances, answers were too vague”
Argentinian dialect	3	“In some instances, there are words that are from Argentinian Spanish”

CONCLUSION

Our work is first in applying LLMs to increase Tuberculosis treatment adherence. We demonstrated how in-context learning can be used to achieve better LLM performance in empathy, medical accuracy, and linguistic accuracy. We introduced an evaluation framework that integrates both technical and clinical aspects necessary for robust LLM tool performance and discussed our findings when designing the system specifically for Argentinian Spanish settings.

GENERATIVE AI USE

We confirm that we did not use generative AI tools/services to author this submission other than occasional use of AI for proofreading.

AUTHOR ATTRIBUTION

Filienko, Daniil: software, methodology, data curation, writing – original draft, writing – review and editing; **Nizar, Mahek:** software, writing – review and editing; **Roberti, Javier:** validation, formal analysis, writing – review and editing; **Galdamez, Denise:** validation, formal analysis, writing – review and editing; **Jakher, Haroon:** validation, formal analysis, writing – review and editing; **Iribarren, Sarah:** conceptualization, supervision, project administration, writing – review and editing; **Yuwen, Weichao:** supervision, resources, writing – review and editing; **De Cock, Martine:** supervision, project administration, writing – review and editing

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